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Features of Training a Modern Fashion Business Manager

Abstract: *Introduction.* The relevance of the study is due to the fact that by integrating into the international educational space, the field of fashion education in Ukraine can comprehend foreign and domestic educational practices, creating modern management training programmes for such a branch of the creative industries as fashion, namely fashion business managers. *Purpose and methods.* The purpose of the article is a theoretical analysis of the peculiarities of training modern fashion business managers in the system of higher education in Ukraine and abroad. The methodological basis of the study is the methods of studying experience and analysis of primary sources and documentation in the field of education, pedagogical modelling. *Results.* The paper analyses the peculiarities of training fashion business managers in the higher education system in Ukraine, in particular, the content of educational programmes and professional growth trajectories, and identifies effective ways to update them based on the experience of specialised fashion and design universities from other countries. It is proved that the training of modern fashion business managers is a flexible, open system aimed at forming a synthesis of individual qualities required by a modern specialist to perform his/her professional functions. *Conclusions.* The scientific novelty lies in the attempt to present an analysis of various educational programmes for the training of fashion business managers in Ukraine, to compare the content of such programmes with approaches to the development of educational programmes in different countries. The practical significance of the results is to understand the existing approaches to the training of fashion business managers in Ukraine in order to modernise and flexibly develop educational programmes in universities.

Keywords: university, fashion industry, fashion business manager, higher education system, educational programme.

1. Introduction

The problem formulation. The existing world of professions in the fashion industry represents a wide variety of creative trajectories and is becoming a very attractive area for the realisation of the creative ambitions of modern youth. For a future university applicant, a passion for fashion business as a career path can start with a simple hobby – imitating fashion, being interested in this topic, having a habit of dressing nicely or creating casual, business, ethnic, creative images, taking photos and posting them on a personal page on social media. A peculiar feature of the twentieth century was the fact that young men and women who wanted to express themselves through their appearance chose many professions related to design, style and fashion. The labour market also needs a wide representation of various fashion professions that perform many functions necessary for its existence, including the professions of designer, stylist, make-up artist, marketer, brand manager, buyer, marketing manager, category manager, sales manager, fashion merchandiser, marketing director, commercial director, brand director, owner of a modelling business or a company in the fashion/beauty spheres, trend analyst, fashion brand stylist, consultant in the design and production of clothing, footwear, accessories, jewellery, face and body care services, fashion journalist, fashion photographer, fashion show director, event manager, etc. (Industriia Mody ta Feshn-Biznes, n.d.). However, despite such a variety of professional trajectories in the fashion sector, graduates of general secondary education institutions in Ukraine do not have a sufficiently formed idea of career opportunities in this sector of the creative industries. This trend persists because higher education in this country is largely focused on industrial and technical skills due to the educational traditions established in previous periods (Fursa, 2011). Yes, it is undoubtedly necessary to get them in the industry, but the current practice of enterprise development in the fashion industry shows that this is not enough to effectively organise your own project, which is quite common in small and medium-sized businesses in this area. Thus, today's experience shows that if we ignore the trends of the fashion business, which is developing dynamically as a result of technical and communication innovations, the students' preparation for professional activities in universities can lag far behind the realities of life. This could be a risk of losing the leading positions of industry-specific domestic universities and an outflow of potentially motivated applicants. It can now be stated that the educational programmes of universities in our country during the last “COVID” and war years have hardly had time to adapt to the needs of the modern fashion industry and labour market, and 90% of young people who receive education in this sector abroad have a strong tendency not to return to Ukraine after graduation (Fashion DNA Ukraine, 2019, p. 10). In all countries

of the world, the training of specialists for professional activities in the fashion industry is based on approaches that are dictated by both the socio-cultural characteristics of each country and the specific problems of the industry itself. The concept of professional education should focus on the understanding of fashion as an integral multi-vector system, and the effectiveness of the educational process of training modern fashion business employees should depend on the balance of conceptual and creative, intellectual and analytical, production and economic areas. The fashion world is not just about creativity and production. In addition to the production component – designers, photographers, stylists, make-up artists – producers of products and services, there are many business professions in the industry along the management “line”, which are often acquired by the producers themselves over time as they develop their business. As they develop their own “fashion project”, they usually realise that it is not enough to design and create a collection; its production needs to be organised, launched, conveyed to the consumer and arranged communication with him/her, as well as regularly maintain and promote the image of the created brand. Without professionals working in the areas of procurement, sales, management, communications and marketing, the work of a designer can go unnoticed. Business professionals in the fashion industry are usually non-public figures, they don't sit in the front rows at fashion shows or give interviews to the media, but it is their decisions that largely determine the vector of development of the fashion industry in their countries. A young person in Ukraine can quickly build a professional career in the industry thanks to quality education and relevant professional experience in the fashion business, as evidenced by various success stories of the Ukrainian fashion industry representatives: for a rather short period it is possible to go through an evolutionary path from establishing your own brand to: LVMH Prize shortlisted (brands Paskal, Anna October, Anton Belinskiy), presenting collections in Paris (Ruslan Baginski), creating commercially successful labels sold in 120 stores around the world, including Bergdorf Goodman in New York, Printemps in Paris, Lane Crawford in Shanghai (IENKI IENKI – Dmytro Yevenko) (Yeremenko & Zvyniatskivska, 2020). During the war years of 2022-2023, many names became famous in the world: Ivan Frolov, who creates concert clothes for Beyoncé, Dua Lipa, Rita Ora, Gwen Stefani and Sam Smith, Ksenia Schneider, who developed the Ukrainian sustainable brand KSENIASCHNAIDER, which together with adidas Originals in 2023 presented the first joint collection that embodies the unique design thinking of the domestic brand “Design without design” in a new look at the classic adidas silhouettes and other bright figures in the domestic fashion business, who can also be called successful managers of their own author's fashion projects.

Countries that are traditionally considered trendsetters in fashion, such as Italy, France, the UK, and the US, have long formed their own systems of support for the fashion business, which can easily include higher education in the fashion sector. This is important in terms of developing fashion businesses in different countries and regions and supporting small and medium-sized enterprises in the industry. Before Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine, this context was typical for us as well: according to researchers from the British Council, in 2017, there were approximately 1000 fashion businesses in Ukraine and about 387 startups were born annually, of which about 10% remained on the market and stood the test of time (*Fashion DNA Ukraine*, 2019). The segment of the fashion design ecosystem in the early 20s of the twenty-first century already included up to 30 university programmes in public and private universities and colleges, including a research (master's) degree programme. At that time, these programmes covered up to 1.5 thousand students (Fursa, 2011; *Fashion DNA Ukraine*, 2019). Fashion business education programmes are still being chosen by students today, in times that are rather unfavourable for peaceful professions. However, despite the difficulties and limitations of offering such programmes in fashion education, modern universities in Ukraine should also focus on the fact that, in addition to “technical skills”, representatives of this industry need to acquire relevant competencies in such crucial for the fashion industry areas as business, finance, production management, ecology, sales, exports, international relations, etc.

State study of the problem. The issue of the quality of fashion specialists' professional education has recently attracted a lot of attention from researchers, especially in the area of design education and comparison of the national education system with educational systems in other countries. For our analysis, the research of the following scholars who draw attention to the need to use educational ideas and technologies from foreign experience, the integration of the concepts of formal and non-formal education in leading foreign fashion and design universities was important (Hardabkhadze, 2018; Danylenko, 2013; Ziablovska, 2021; Melnyk, 2016). The historical aspects of studying design education development in Ukraine and abroad, and modeling the content of professional training of design specialists in art educational institutions are also covered by O. Fursa (2011) publications. The study of V. Babenko and V. Harashchenko (2022) is generally devoted to the fashion industry as a component of the creative industries in Ukraine and also reveals the impact of fashion on the formation of creative capital. The authors draw an important conclusion that the Ukrainian fashion industry is a new market segment and commercial component, which as a separate sector of the economy is gaining more and more development and includes the production and sale of goods and related services. The study notes that the modern development of creative

industries is becoming an impetus for the realisation of creative abilities and ideas of the creative class, which is also valuable for our further analysis. The idea of introducing various forms of non-formal art education in the fashion sector and continuing its trajectory “throughout life” (Leshchenko & Sulaieva, 2017), which has hardly been mentioned in the scientific discourse, also requires special attention. This opinion seems important in ensuring a professional approach to the continuous professional development and effective performance of a competitive specialist within the framework of intensifying the life and professional skills acquired by him/her in the fashion management ecosystem.

Unresolved issues. Thus, the problem of approaches to the development of the content of higher education programmes in the field of fashion business in Ukraine has hardly been studied. Given the dynamism of changes that characterise the fashion industry itself, such programmes should undoubtedly have signs of flexibility and constant updating and transformation, which make it possible to develop the content of education along with changes in society and to adapt the training of specialists to the demands of the labour market. Taking into account these trends in the development and management of educational programmes in universities will contribute to the quality of preparation for professional activity of effective fashion business managers who will be ready to solve management tasks of any level of complexity.

2. Purpose and methods

The purpose and research tasks. The purpose of the article is to analyse the content of educational programmes in higher education institutions that train fashion business managers in Ukraine and abroad, as well as to identify the peculiarities of modern educational training of fashion business specialists and to provide recommendations on conceptual approaches to the composition of content components in such educational programmes in Ukrainian universities.

Achieving this purpose involves solving the following tasks:

- to reveal the peculiarities of training a modern fashion business manager in the system of domestic and foreign higher education;
- to identify the strengths of formal and non-formal types of education in the field of fashion business;
- to consider the possibilities of using foreign experience, effective approaches from the field of non-formal education to the development of relevant educational programmes in domestic universities.

Methodology and methods. The methodological basis of the study is a systematic approach to studying the peculiarities of training managers in the fashion business. It was based on the principles that allowed us to consider educational programmes based on a competency-based approach to the design of educational programmes and the use of student-centred learning principles.

To achieve the purpose and solve the tasks of the study, the following methods were used: general theoretical: analytical and synthetic review of the literature on the research problem, as well as analysis of various sources – normative educational documents, web resources of educational institutions, as well as other operators of non-formal educational services, which publicly available information on existing educational programmes and their content; systematisation, classification, comparison, generalisation, interpretation of the data obtained on the outlined issues; the method of analogue modelling, with the help of which proposals for the modernisation of domestic educational programmes in universities that provide training in the field of fashion business management have been developed.

Information base. The information base of the research is based on the scientific works of scientists in pedagogy and management, regulatory documents on educational training in universities, analytical reports, official websites of educational institutions and government agencies. The empirical substantiation of the main conceptual provisions for changing educational programmes for fashion business managers is based on the results of the analysis of the content of programmes of domestic and foreign universities and the conclusions drawn on it.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Peculiarities of training a modern fashion business manager in the education system of Ukraine

For a general understanding of educational trajectories for the training of future fashion business managers in Ukraine, let's analyse the situation in the educational sector at all levels. For a long time, the formal education system in Ukraine did not have a diverse system of education in the field of fashion business. It should be noted that formal education is education provided in the system of secondary schools, vocational colleges, universities, and other formal educational institutions and continues in our country, usually until a young person reaches the age of 25, if the applicant is preparing immediately after completing secondary education (Vovk et al., 2019). The education reforms that began as a result of Ukraine's European integration in formal educational institutions gave impetus to the creation of educational programmes based on a competence-based approach, which “made it possible to strengthen the professional and applied orientation of educational services, their effectiveness, and to target the professional training of graduates for their future employment” (Sharov, 2018, p. 196). Thus, the developers of educational programmes at state universities are guided by the standards of professional higher education approved in 2018 –2021 for the training of both professional junior bachelors

and standards for the training of specialists with higher education – bachelors and masters, related to specialties whose graduates work in the fashion industry. These are the following specialties in field 02 “Culture and Arts” – 022 “Design”, 023 “Fine Arts, Decorative Arts, Restoration”, 028 “Management of Socio-Cultural Activities”. Usually, the training of fashion specialists includes specialties from other fields: 07 “Management and Administration” and 18 “Production and Technology”, including: 073 “Management”, 076 “Entrepreneurship, Trade and Exchange Activities”, 182 “Light Industry Technologies”. In general, education standards are a new generation of sectoral standards for both vocational pre-university and higher education. They were developed to improve the efficiency of graduates of different levels in the labour market and are designed to restore the link between these levels of education and the professional sphere. Since their adoption, the standards have given a significant positive impetus to the radical renewal of educational programmes in formal education institutions – colleges and universities (Zatverdzheni Standarty, n.d.; Zatverdzheni Standarty Vysheoi Osvity, n.d.).

As of 2023, the Unified State Electronic Database on Education in the Register of Educational Institutions contains the names of 17 institutions of higher education offering training programmes for managers under the study programme 028 “Management of Socio-Cultural Activities” (Reiestr Subiektiv Osvitnoi Diialnosti, n.d.). However, the analysis of the content of their educational programmes at the level of professional junior bachelor shows that colleges do not provide such training (*Table 1*).

Art colleges follow the traditions of training specialists in the club sector, which was extensive in Soviet times, and most often offer educational programmes in the socio-cultural or artistic sphere in the “Management of Socio-Cultural Activities” speciality (11 art colleges in total). According to the analysis of the educational programmes presented on the websites of educational institutions, the disciplines that form the professional competences of graduates include such management subjects as “Management of Socio-Cultural Activities”, “Project Management”, and “Communication Management”.

At the same time, it can be noted that in the very trajectory of education, the “start” of a professional career in the fashion industry begins with “production” professions related to design and art, rather than “managerial” qualifications. In college curricula, the “starting” programmes for a fashion specialist are those that teach various types of design, such as fashion design, footwear design, hair and make-up design, style and make-up design, graphic design, art painting, artistic embroidery, leather goods, metal jewellery, etc. As can be seen from the names of the educational programmes on the websites of the institutions, vocational colleges mainly focus on the production aspect of training fashion business specialists in the specialties 022 “Design” (42 insti-

tutions), 023 “Fine Arts, Decorative Arts, Restoration” (28 institutions). To continue their education, graduates of such programmes can potentially choose the paths of professions in the fashion industry and, in particular, management in it. Among the cycle of educational components of professional and practical training, elective subjects, there may be compositions of such programmes, which hardly ever include business-oriented subjects. At the same time, there are educational programmes that include such subjects both in the cycle of professional training and in elective subjects. These are subjects such as “Economics and Business Organisation”, “Fundamentals of Entrepreneurship and Management”, and “Advertising”.

Table 1. Examples of study programmes for professional junior bachelors majoring in “Management of socio-cultural activities”

Educational establishment	Educational programme	Qualification
Oleksandriia Professional College of Culture and Arts	Spectacular theatrical events. Folk song art. Folk instrumental art	Organiser of socio-cultural activities, Head of an amateur creative team
Lviv Professional College of Culture and Arts	Film, photo and video production. Organisation of the leisure industry	Organiser of cultural and leisure activities
Kamianets-Podilskyi Professional College of Culture and Arts	Song art. Wind and folk instruments. Spectacular and theatrical events. Film, photo and video production	Organiser of socio-cultural activities, Head of an amateur creative team
Nizhyn Mariia Zankovetska Applied College of Culture and Arts	Organisation of the instrumental group (folk / wind and percussion instruments). Organisation of the activity of a vocal group (folk singing). Organisation of entertainment and theatrical events. Organisation of tourist services	Organiser of socio-cultural activities, Head of an amateur creative team, orchestra/choir artist, tourist services specialist

Source: created by the authors based on the websites of the institutions (Kamianets-Podilskyi Professional College of Culture and Arts, n.d.; Lviv Professional College of Culture and Arts, n.d.; Nizhyn Maria Zankovetska Applied College of Culture and Arts, n.d.; Oleksandriia Professional Culture and Art College, n.d.)

At the bachelor's and/or master's level, this situation changes dramatically and educational programmes for fashion business managers become more specialised. However, it should be noted that specialists can also be trained

according to different standards of higher education: field of knowledge 02 “Culture and Arts” – speciality 028 “Management of Socio-Cultural Activities” (28 institutions) and field of knowledge 07 “Management and Administration” – speciality 073 “Management” (211 institutions). For example, at Poltava University of Economics and Trade, in the 2nd year of the Bachelor's degree programme “Management. Business Administration”, students are offered the discipline “Management of the Fashion Industry” (5 ECTS credits – 150 hours) (Sylabus Navchalnoi Dystsypliny, 2021). The course covers such topics as fashion theory and history, fashion industry technologies, fashion and design trends, fashion business management and value creation, assortment design and concept development, brand management in the fashion industry, logistics management, the role of buyers and merchandisers in the fashion industry, fashion and digital trends promotion, and customer experience management.

In Ukraine, only two higher education institutions have narrow-profile educational programmes in “Fashion Business Management”: the state university Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts (Yedyna Modna Kafedra, n.d.) and the private higher education institution Kyiv University of Culture (Industriia Mody ta Feshn-Biznes, n.d.). These universities are classical universities of culture and art that offer a range of different educational programmes in this area, including training in the management competences of cultural professionals. Universities with “production traditions” tend to create more production-oriented programmes designed for practitioners rather than managers. For example, Kyiv National University of Technology and Design (n.d.) for both bachelors and masters offers fashion-oriented educational programs in the specialty 075 “Marketing” “Digital marketing”, educational programs in the field 18 “Production and technologies” in the specialty 182 “Technologies of light industry”, namely “Textile technologies of fashion and interior space”, “Computer design in the fashion industry”, “Design and technology of sewing products”, “Modeling, design and artistic decoration of light industry products”, “Fashion industry”. The last of these programmes is aimed at training bachelors in the field of knowledge as direct performers – bachelors in light industry technologies (designers, fashion designers, stylists, image makers, visual merchandisers, decorators, costume designers, designers-technologists, trend analysts, buyers). As you can see in the list of professions offered to graduates, there is the profession of a buyer, who is a procurement manager by his functions and is responsible for the rational use of the company's budget, market research and the purchase of goods that bring guaranteed profit. As a result of training, in addition to developing models, creating fashion projects, collections, concepts of design projects, studying the principles of presentation, taking into account fashion trends, students learn entrepreneurial skills and the basics of creating their own business, using PR technologies

(Kyiv National University of Technology and Design, n.d.). Lutsk National Technical University offers a bachelor's degree programme in Fashion Industry, speciality 182 “Technologies of Light Industry”, graduates of which can work as confectioners, technicians in textile and light industry, technologists, designers, craftsmen, and site managers, and the Master's degree programme “Technology and Design in the Fashion Industry”, graduates of which can work as experts in finished products, process engineers, design engineers, research engineers, consultants, researchers, teachers (Osvitnia Prohrama, 2022; Osvitnia Prohrama, 2023).

The master's programme of the private university “International University of Finance” (hereinafter – IUF) is an effective in terms of content for training a manager in the fashion industry – the MBA programme “Management in the Fashion Industry” (MBA Prohrama, n.d.). The programme is designed to meet the needs of the global fashion industry, which is highly complex and competitive, is multidisciplinary in nature and provides a systematic study of applied sciences and industrial operations in a global context. This is the only integrated MBA course in strategic fashion management in Ukraine, delivered by a team of national fashion management leaders and the best MUF lecturers. The programme is divided into four modules over 24 months. Between modules, students complete individual and group assignments through distance learning. In the final phase of the programme, students are required to write a practice-oriented master's thesis. However, the subject matter of the research is determined by an applied problem that exists directly in their own business organisation or professional fashion environment.

Consequently, there are few programmes for training managers for the fashion industry in Ukraine. Despite the trend towards studying applied sciences and industrial operations in a global context, they are still dominated by an academic context rather than a practice-oriented one, such as writing a master's thesis, which is research-based and hardly focused on running a business and managing your own project.

The content of professional training programmes at universities has also been significantly influenced by such an educational trend as dual education. Today, dual education is a factor in the modernisation of approaches to education in modern universities as a result of education systems solving key applied tasks: providing quality educational services in accordance with the requirements of society and the market; providing graduates with quality employment opportunities upon completion of educational programmes at universities. For the national system of fashion education, these issues are quite relevant. Because most educational institutions as social systems, as mentioned above, are aimed at reproducing past practices rather than transforming the content of education as an effective response to the demands of

business and society. The Strategy for the Development of Higher Education in Ukraine for 2022 – 2032 states that employers are not sufficiently involved in the development of higher education institutions, whose educational programmes should be flexible, modular, focused on solving specific applied tasks, and take into account the requirements for enhanced practical training (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2022). Therefore, dual education is a model of education that provides for a consistent transition from authoritarian reproductive education to innovative research-based education that is guided by world standards. For example, studying design programmes in Danish educational institutions is characterised by a significant practical orientation, active cooperation with enterprises and government agencies (Ziablovska, 2021, p. 116).

At the same time, today the use of various types of educational activities in fashion education, including non-formal education, is due to the new educational paradigm, the main idea of which is the transition from “lifelong learning” to “lifelong learning” (Leshchenko & Sulaieva, 2017). In the last decade, domestic scholars and practitioners have increasingly paid attention to non-formal education, which is any organised and continuous educational activity that can be carried out within and outside educational institutions and is accessible to people of any age. This type of education can cover a large number of different educational programmes that are not necessarily built into the system of “steps” of the National Qualification Framework levels. In response to the needs of the professional fashion environment in the fashion education system in Ukraine, this “niche” is being filled by the following educational projects that, in the content of their activities, try to compensate for the “losses” of formal education in fashion training to form relevant competencies in fashion business management. The programmes that offer such projects are shorter in terms of the time required for students to complete them, more relevant in terms of content, and more market-oriented. The teachers involved in the implementation of the content of education in such programmes include a significant number of professionals with a promoted professional “name”, an established image and authority in the fashion industry and/or a sustainable business/brand, etc. And this means a high degree of trust among students in their professional competence and the relevance of the programmes. Nowadays, such programmes are offered in different formats: offline, blended, online. They are not separately certified or verified by state institutions, are less long than a bachelor's or master's degree, and are commercial in nature, as they are designed to involve highly expert teachers and, accordingly, the uniqueness of the educational content. And this means a high degree of trust among students in their professional competence and the relevance of the programmes. Nowadays, such programmes are offered in different formats: offline, blended, online. They are not separately certified or verified

by state institutions, are less long than a bachelor's or master's degree, and are commercial in nature, as they are designed to involve highly expert teachers and, accordingly, the uniqueness of the educational content. Their main value lies in the educational trend of “life long learning”; and is associated with the actualisation of professional development of narrow competencies in the speciality. Examples of educational projects that offer similar educational programmes include: Kyiv Academy of Media Arts, Ukrainian Fashion Education Group, Fashion Law & Business Course (ILTI-School), Academy of Style and Design by Andre Tan (*Table 2*).

Table 2. Examples of educational programmes in fashion business from non-formal education operators in Ukraine

Platform name	Course name	Educational programme content, main course topics
Kyiv Academy of Media Arts	Fashion	Fashion as a social phenomenon. Analytics tools. History of fashion. Fashion trends, lifestyle. Fashion journalism and PR. Fashion shows. Fashion styling and photography
Ukrainian Fashion Education Group	90 courses	Fashion system, fashion trends. Creating and presenting collections. DNA, emotions and values, internationalisation, structure and management of a fashion brand. Features of working with ethnicity. Social networks, fashion logo. Business strategy for brand development. Assortment matrix, work with agents, buyers. The role of the creative director. Innovative products of a modern fashion brand
ILTI-School	Fashion law & business	Global courses in fashion law. Organisational and legal form of doing business. Relationships with partners and investors. Collaborations. Franchising. Contracts (manufacturers, designers, photographers, models). Copyright. Brands and celebrities. Customs and the fashion industry. Fashion, science and technology
Academy of style and design by Andre Tan	Creating a fashion brand	Fashion industry. Stages of creating a brand, collection, and promotion. Brand philosophy. Technical aspects. Lookbook styles and catalogues. Work with the media

Source: created by the authors based on the websites of the institutions (Academy of Style and Design by Andre Tan, 2022; Institute of Law Technology & Innovation, n.d.; Kyiv Academy of Media Arts, n.d.; Ukrainian Fashion Education Group, n.d.)

Thus, the content of these educational courses is focused on trends in fashion and business, and is practically oriented. Thanks to the tasks that students perform during their studies, they have the opportunity to acquire a

wide range of practical skills. These are usually individually tailored programmes that are adapted to the intentions and needs of the students or to the business they have already established in the fashion industry.

Along with such informal educational projects, meaningful forms of presenting professional information are also gaining ground, with signs of efficiency and exclusivity, which is highly valued by professionals in this rather fast-moving business sector. These are more informational than educational professional channels on social media and messengers that can be used to develop professional competencies as a means of self-education – an informational type of education. They also perform an “educational function” for professionals, but not directly, but indirectly, increasing the competence of those who systematically engage in information through the content of such channels. For fashion professionals, Telegram, TikTok and Instagram have become such platforms. In Ukraine, the network of such professional fashion channels is not yet sufficiently formed and does not have a promoted educational image. However, our research of certain highly specialised Ukrainian-language fashion platforms on Telegram showed that they have high-quality and timely fashion content that is read by thousands of professionals. For example, the following channels can be identified: In bold (Zhyrnym Shryftom, n.d.): a channel of professional fashion journalist Roman Tymofieiev about the Ukrainian fashion industry and not only (10198 users), Fashion Law (n.d.): fashion cases and law in the fashion industry (6597 users), Fashion Digital Ukraine (n.d.): a channel about trends from the world of fashion, contemporary art, technology, business (3028 users), Cimetière (n.d.): about Ukrainian fashion & culture (8199 users), Ukrainian Fashion (n.d.): a community of the Ukrainian fashion industry (5349 users), Fashion press (n.d.): digital copies of branded fashion magazines published in different countries (1024 users), etc.

Informal educational resources for advanced training and the acquisition of special competencies in the fashion business also include courses on social media, educational platforms, webinars and masterclasses from fashion industry practitioners. Such courses allow you to learn what is needed to create a commercially successful product, how the fashion system works, how trends are formed, what should be in the fashion assortment, how to calculate the cost of a collection, and much more. The peculiarity of non-formal education in the fashion business is that the key questions and challenges facing the fashion industry today will be answered by those who directly create it: designers, businessmen, journalists, marketers, founders of the largest fashion projects. The experience of those who have practice, especially in such matters as business, is a key component for a fundamental understanding of the holistic process. After all, without business knowledge and the whole system, where all the components and their interactions are understood, it is impossible to develop

even the most interesting idea. Therefore, such courses are an introduction to the main sections of the fashion business, which is relevant for most fashion professionals from designers and founders of fashion brands to marketers, stylists, brand managers and those who want to create their own fashion business.

Examples of non-formal education include self-education: reading books on the fashion industry, building your own brand, fashion management, etc., watching videos and interviews on the fashion business, reading articles and analytical reviews published by various companies and enterprises in the fashion sector, reading fashion magazines and other media covering transformations and current events in the fashion sector. You can also add watching Instagram feeds of famous designers and fashion houses, specialists from various parts of the fashion industry, which will allow you to better understand the structure of the industry, improve your own knowledge and increase awareness of new products and trends.

Thus, domestic educational programmes for the training of a modern fashion business specialist are aimed at: developing the skills and attributes of a specialist necessary for successful work in the fashion business; educating leaders in the fashion industry; acquiring practical skills and providing access to leading companies and networks in the fashion industry; gaining practical experience and the latest knowledge in the field of fashion industry management by providing opportunities to work with industry experts and meet them throughout the study period, participating in projects focused on professional development in the fashion industry; developing your own holistic view of the fashion industry; and a wide range of career opportunities in logistics, supply chain, merchandising, marketing and other areas of fashion management. Our analysis has shown that the training of management specialists for the fashion industry in our country at the present stage should cover all types of education: formal, non-formal and informal, and follows different trajectories. At the bachelor's and master's level, Ukrainian universities offer interesting programmes for training fashion business managers, but there is no sustainable model of a national university leading the way in training specialists for the industry – a comprehensive fashion university that could occupy this niche in the educational market, providing both production, design and specialised management training, as well as lifelong learning for fashion industry professionals.

3.2. Peculiarities of modern fashion business manager training in the system of foreign education

The most popular countries in the world where you can get relevant competencies in fashion, design, fashion business, photography, fashion illustration, styling, and marketing management in the fashion industry are Italy,

France, the United Kingdom, and the United States. These countries have developed educational systems that allow them to “respond” to the trends of the creative economy, which combine fashion products developers and manufacturers, suppliers of resources (raw materials, information, intellectual, marketing, creative), innovations and technologies (FashTech), promotion, sales and service (Budnikevych & Duziak, 2022). The combination of commercial, technological, and creative components in the context of the fashion market development makes it possible to understand the main trends in which a fashion brand, which is the author of a design idea, combines with marketing technologies to promote a fashion product or service. And this is reflected in the content of educational programmes offered by modern universities abroad. We have analysed such programmes and presented a summary of their content, which is presented in the table (*Table 3*).

As for the educational programmes for training specialists in the field of fashion business in foreign universities, it can be noted that among them some train specialists exclusively for the fashion industry, such as the Italian Istituto Marangoni. This is due to a significant variety of training areas (specialisations, educational programmes for fashion professionals with different educational needs), which last from 1 to 4 years (bachelor's, master's, postgraduate studies, courses). This has a positive impact on the motivation of students to acquire knowledge at different levels and stages of training and establish further cooperation in the industry, etc. For comparison, in Ukraine, fashion business specialists are trained in educational institutions as a separate area of management or production of a fashion product or service, as mentioned earlier. Another Italian university, Domus Academy (Domus Academy Milano, n.d.), demonstrates an interesting and innovative approach to training specialists in the field of fashion business. For example, in the Master in Business Design course, students learn to establish relationships between business and the world of design, get to know the principles of large, medium, and small businesses, draw up company development plans, and learn marketing, branding, and communications. The programme consists of lectures and seminars, practical work with the programme manager, a mentor and an individual coach. By the end of the course, each student develops their own portfolio.

Studying at the Mod'Art International Paris High School also focuses on the practical skills of its graduates: among the popular disciplines are fashion design, fashion management, graphic design, and visual merchandising. Already during their studies, students can launch their own clothing line or implement an author's project (Mod'Art International, n.d.).

The peculiarity of training a modern fashion business specialist in the UK is the approach to fashion as a business. Thus, students at the London College of Fashion are primarily focused on career and professional success.

Table 3. Examples of study programmes in fashion business in foreign universities

Names	Generalised areas of study programmes
<i>Italy</i>	
Istituto Marangoni. Domus Academy. Polimoda. Accademia Costume & Moda. Accademia Italiana. Instituto Europeo de Diseño	Design of clothes, footwear, accessories, textiles, thinking: techniques and materials, design methods. History of fashion, art, applied arts. Fashion illustration, fashion photography. Fashion style, styling and visual merchandising. Forecasting fashion trends, international business, markets. Fashion marketing, fashion product management, fashion buying. Creative management: business models and expertise, analytics. Digital marketing, visual identity, their tools. Integrated communication strategies, advertising. Fashion law, legislation and economics. Fashion sustainability and industrial evolution, innovation, technology
<i>France</i>	
LISAA (L'Institut Supérieur des Arts Appliqués). Mod'Art International Paris	Fashion and textile design. Brand creation, image, fashion and luxury management. Buying and logistics, international fashion marketing. Intercultural management, merchandising, wholesale and retail trade. Communication and digital marketing, social media, press. Style and products, sustainability, consumer behaviour
<i>Great Britain</i>	
University of Brighton. Arts University Bournemouth. Westminster University. Glasgow Caledonian University. London College of Fashion	Intercultural history of art and design. Approaches and practices in art and fashion design. Cultural policy of fashion, branding and fashion communication. Fashion photography, styling, fashion illustration. Marketing, visual promotion, business planning. Market and business research, ethics. Creative collaboration in the fashion industry, trend forecasting. Design and innovation, digital fashion innovation. Individual practices in an interdisciplinary framework, historical influences and current socio-political issues. Strategic management in the fashion business, creative team
<i>USA</i>	
Academy of Art University. Fashion Institute of Technology	Fashion illustration, fashion design, fashion product design. Art history, fashion history, communication. Advertising and digital design, digitalisation. Entrepreneurship, concept development. Culture and international business, legal principles, financial management. International production, applied research. Microeconomics, business plan, ethics, innovation. Sustainability, strategies in business communication, leadership

Source: created by the authors based on the websites of the above universities (Academy of Art University, n.d.; Accademia Costume & Moda, n.d.; Accademia Italiana, n.d.; Arts University Bournemouth, n.d.; Domus Academy Milano, n.d.; Fashion Institute of Technology, n.d.; Glasgow Caledonian University, n.d.; Instituto Europeo de Diseño, n.d.; Istituto Marangoni, n.d.; L'Institut Supérieur des Arts Appliqués, n.d.; London College of Fashion, n.d.; Mod'Art International, n.d.; Polimoda, n.d.; University of Brighton, n.d.; University of Westminster, n.d.)

A special mentoring scheme helps them to do this: students are assigned to fashion practitioners who guide the process of becoming aspiring designers (London College of Fashion, n.d.).

As already mentioned, the system of studying abroad is focused on replenishing one's own experience and building a professional portfolio. Unfortunately, in Ukraine, the education system is focused on the preparation and defence of bachelor's and master's theses at the end of the educational programme. Such works are a significant contribution to the scientific development of certain issues in the fashion industry and allow a future specialist to determine the range of interests and subject matter for further creative research, but they are of rather low practical value – usually a future fashion manager cannot present their work during an interview with a potential employer. Therefore, along with research, it is advisable to create a practical project under the guidance of an experienced mentor (support for a fashion project or company, creating your own business plan for a fashion company, organising a show on your own, etc.) It is also important to pay attention to the formation of a “managerial portfolio” as an experience of achievements in specific projects during the years of study at the university. In other words, the Ukrainian system of training fashion business professionals lacks practical elements that would demonstrate not only theoretical knowledge of fashion, but also the creativity and practical skills of graduates.

The system of training fashion business managers abroad is generally characterised by a high degree of variability in the areas of training (specialities) in which training is provided. This has a positive impact on the level of knowledge of students and future professionals and on the establishment of further cooperation between them. For example, at Istituto Marangoni, students learn the basics of management in the fashion business and pricing, how to position a product and collection in a highly competitive market, analyse the work of competitors and the principles of leading brands, and consider fashion concerning the development of art, music, design, and marketing. Using examples from well-known brands, students explore the main factors that influence success in the industry. The study programmes include subjects such as brand marketing, licensing strategies, fashion panorama, fashion sociology, financial management and financial control. For example, Istituto Marangoni offers a semester-long postgraduate programme in Buying & Merchandising. The course consists of the following subjects: introduction to procurement, understanding of procurement processes, the fashion industry system, digital marketing, business development in the fashion industry, modern procurement, procurement and merchandising techniques. By the end of the programme, students develop a purchasing plan and a profit plan based on various data, including sales figures and fashion trends. Graduates of fashion business pro-

grammes can hold management positions in various fields, including business plan development, design and innovation management, and communication strategies. After graduating from one of the business programmes, you can get a job in a fashion house, branding agency, service or consulting company, or start your own business (Istituto Marangoni, n.d.).

As for non-formal education, it can be divided into two categories: 1) courses from leading universities and fashion companies or communities aimed at improving skills or expanding the knowledge base in the fashion industry, upon completion of which the student receives a certificate; 2) master classes, workshops, webinars from representatives of the fashion industry, which are also aimed at improving skills or expanding the knowledge base in the fashion industry. Examples of non-formal education operators in the field of the fashion business, after completing which a student will receive a certificate of completion of the educational programme and qualification, are: Luxury Brand Marketing and International Management from Paris Fashion Academy, Build Your Fashion Empire from Future London Academy, Creative Direction from Conde Nast College and others.

Thus, the analysis of the above examples of educational programmes allowed us to identify the main features of training a modern fashion business manager abroad, namely:

- the multidisciplinary nature of the content of education, focused on constant changes in the fashion industry, a thorough knowledge of the panorama of fashion as a creative industry, the provision of practical skills focused on combining management, procurement, retail, supply chain, marketing, and communications;

- close connection of fashion management training with design and fashion practice through case studies, research, internships, innovation and the provision of learning experiences based on multidisciplinary research (especially in material handling) and reflective practice of short-term projects that help to understand and evaluate critical factors for organising individual and/or corporate activities in the fashion industry;

- understanding the importance of marketing and its relevance to fashion through the introduction of key marketing practices and the creation of an individual marketing plan;

- expanding opportunities for “global” employment of graduates in the industry;

- fostering a culture of continuous professional development through short-term relevant lifelong learning programmes at leading fashion universities;

- systematic interaction with teachers through assessment of educational performance, formative assessment, creation and filling of a meaningful portfolio during training, participation in projects, and a special scheme for mentoring from fashion practitioners.

4. Conclusions

The results of the conducted research allow us to draw the following conclusions.

1. The fashion business at the present stage of society development is one of the determining factors of economic, political, cultural, and social development. Management in the fashion sector requires specialists who can fulfil their tasks at the level of current economic and creative requirements.

2. The modern fashion market requires a specialist to possess a range of competencies: from understanding all aspects of production to innovative promotion technologies. To master them, there are many educational programmes for training a modern fashion business specialist, which include different types of education: formal (studying at academies and universities to obtain a certain qualification in the fashion industry), non-formal (courses, webinars, master classes, workshops) and informal (self education) and require “life-long learning”.

3. Domestic educational programmes for training a modern fashion business specialist are aimed at developing the skills and attributes necessary for successful work in the fashion business; educating leaders in the fashion industry; gaining practical skills from leading fashion designers and providing access to leading companies and networks in the fashion industry; gaining practical experience and the latest knowledge in the field of fashion industry management through opportunities to work with industry experts and meet them throughout the study period, participating in projects; developing a holistic view of the fashion industry and a wide range of career opportunities in logistics, supply chain, merchandising, marketing and other areas of management in the fashion industry.

4. The training of specialists for the fashion industry in all countries of the world is based on approaches dictated by their socio-cultural characteristics and industry problems but there is a clear common system based on integrative approaches: innovation of fashion business strategies, flexibility, and adaptation to modern industry requirements, awareness of management and operational activities of the fashion business, knowledge of the structure and current trends in the industry, creativity and ingenuity, ability to work with the audience, financial and legal literacy in managing fashion projects, ability to promote the product and build local and global communications.

5. The peculiarities of training a modern fashion business manager in the system of domestic and foreign higher education include:

- “non-linearity” of managerial training, which involves different trajectories of education and an integrated approach that combines production and management competencies;

- foreign universities also widely offer postgraduate short-term programmes that allow fashion business professionals to acquire relevant compe-

tencies. This allows universities to remain leaders in the fashion management education market and implement research projects related to the innovations introduction in the fashion industry.

The scientific novelty. The scientific novelty of the obtained results lies in the comparative characterisation of the system of training fashion business managers in Ukraine and abroad and the identification of their leading features to ensure the implementation of an up-to-date competence-based business approach.

The significance of the study. The practical significance of the results obtained is manifested in the use of these approaches in the preparation of domestic educational programmes for training fashion managers with maximum involvement of the practical component, which is based on the main aspects of the fashion business: 1) production and use of raw materials for the further manufacture of fashion products; 2) production of fashion goods and introduction of services; 3) marketing of manufactured products and sale of services; 4) promotion and popularisation of manufactured fashion products or services; 5) ensuring the competitiveness of fashion products or services.

Prospects for further research. Prospects for further research in this area are to create practice-oriented flexible educational courses for the training of fashion managers in Ukraine.

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